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JUSTIFICATION OF MINING AND ENVIRONMENTAL SAFETY OF UNDERGROUND MINING OF COMPLEX-STRUCTURAL ORE DEPOSITS USING INTEGRATED METHODS

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The article discusses the issues of substantiating the mining, technical and environmental safety of underground mining of complex-structured ore deposits using complex integrated methods. Graphic-analytical methods (nomograms and calculation formulas) are proposed for calculating the stable parameters of outcrops of host rocks and backfill material of various compositions and strengths during their undermining and extinguishing technogenic voids. A systematic approach was used, which contains an analysis of the results of research and design work on the development of new technologies and technical means using standard and new methods. A functional relationship has been established between the magnitude of the stresses of the rock mass and the number of pulses (sounds of destruction) per minute, which characterize its structural (**a**) and strength (**b**) properties, which is described by a curvilinear dependence of the form $y = ax^b$. A classification of the stressed state of a rock mass according to the degree of impact hazard is proposed (non-impact hazardous, with $\eta \leq 0.2$; the first, second and third categories of impact hazard, respectively, with $\eta > 0.5$; $0.3 < \eta \leq 0.5$ and $0.2 < \eta \leq 0.3$) depending on the shape and intensity of the disturbance, the orientation of the maximum stresses σ_{max} (vertical, horizontal or tangential to the surface of the disturbance) relative to the workings. "Instructions for the geomechanical justification of the safe mining of reserves in the mines of the State Enterprise "VostGOK" have also been compiled," Ukraine and "Instructions for geomechanical justification for the safe development of reserves above the mountains. –300 m at the State Enterprise "Direction" mine (SE "VostGOK", Ukraine). It is proposed to continue research and provide appropriate funds (at the expense of enterprises, local and central government bodies) for carrying out urgent environmental and social measures. It is proposed to continue research and provide appropriate funds (at the expense of enterprises, local and central government bodies) for carrying out urgent environmental and social measures when mining of ferrous, non-ferrous and radioactive metals. This will improve the mining, technical and environmental safety of work, rational use, protection of subsoil, the natural environment and the population living in the zone of influence of underground mining of ore deposits. Canada, German, the Republic of Kazakhstan, Ukraine and other developed mining countries of the world.

Keywords: ore deposits, underground mining, energy-disturbed massifs, mining and environmental safety.

Introduction

The practice of exploration for deposits localized in rock masses proved that the well-known Protodyakonov's theory is more applicable to manage their condition (1933) [1]. In accordance with this theory only the mass of rocks enclosed within the arch affects the workings. The arch height is significantly less than the depth of works. This theory will be further specified. In particular, V.D. Slesarev (1948) [2] established the decisive parameter - the tensile strength of the rocks forming the beam; A.A. Borisov (1980) [3] linked it to the stability of the rock layer in the roof of the mine; S.V. Vetrov (1975) [4] defined the stable position of the working as the equality between the strength of the

wedged rocks forming a hinged arch as a massif within the arch of natural equilibrium. Subsequently, it was determined that the preservation of the earth's surface from destruction is ensured by regulating the level of stress in areas of different strengths, the interconnection of ore extraction in time, space and the degree of its preparedness for mining, and on this basis, new nature- and resource-saving technologies were proposed that gave positive results in underground mining complex-structured ore deposits in energy-disturbed massifs of Ukraine, the Republic of Kazakhstan, Canada and other developed mining countries of the world [5]. Therefore, increasing the safety of underground mining of such de-

posits, taking into account the geomechanical justification of optimal parameters and mining schemes, rational methods of controlling rock pressure, the strength and composition of the hardening backfill mixture, the procedure for mining ore deposits, the economically feasible intensity of production processes that ensure the safety of the earth's surface and residential facilities development in the zone of influence of mining operations is an important scientific, practical and social problem that requires a prompt solution [6]. This work is a continuation of research, the main scientific and practical results of which are given in more detail in [7].

The purpose of the research is - substantiate the mining, technical and environmental safety of underground mining of complex-structured ore deposits using integrated methods, taking into account the geomechanical state of energy-damaged massifs, stable parameters of host rock outcrops and backfill material during their undermining. This will ensure rational use and protection of subsoil, the natural environment and the population living in the zone of influence of mining production.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were solved:

1. Establish the possibility of preserving the earth's surface from destruction during technogenic intervention in the rock massif.
2. To develop a graphic-analytical method for determining the safe parameters of chambers when developing ore deposits of complex structure.
3. Recommend the parameters of chamber mining systems with backfill for underground mining of ore deposits of complex structure.

Research methods. The authors conducted a technological audit and analyzed previously conducted studies and control observations, mathematical and physical modeling in the field of development of methods, technical means for creating nature- and resource-saving technologies that ensure increased mining, technical and environmental safety of deposit development in energy-disturbed massifs, laboratory studies and mine experiments, mathematical and physical modeling, as well as theoretical analysis and generalization of the results of studies of geomechanical and seismic monitoring data using standard and new methods with the participation of the authors [8].

Manuscript structure

Analysis of the latest research and publications. The issues of managing the stress-strain state (SSS) of a rock mass were also dealt with in the Republic of Kazakhstan, in particular by the Eastern Scientific Research Mining and Metallurgical Institute of Non-Ferrous Metals (JSC VNIKMET). Abroad, the above-mentioned studies were conducted in the USA, Germany, France, Chile and Australia. The results of the analysis allow us to conclude that the formation of man-made voids is important for solving this issue. This affects the occurrence and redistribution of SSS of the rock mass, and also helps to increase the technological and environmental safety of the environment in the area affected by mining operations [9].

Statement of the problem and its solution.

Determination of the main parameters and dimensions of the cameras. The geometric parameters of the chambers must ensure the stability of the massif outcrops without significant collapses (no more than 300 m³) preventing the development of reserves of the production block. The authors divide methods for determining the geometric parameters of cameras into two groups: analytical and empirical. Analytical methods are based on the principles of the theory of elasticity and plasticity, but ignorance of the initial stress state and insufficient accuracy of the constants of the physical and mechanical properties of the massif reduce the effectiveness of these methods [10]. An empirical method based on the use of graphical data analysis using patterns and functional dependencies. Examples are the methods of functional characteristics for justifying the geometric parameters of floor-chamber mining systems in Krivbass (Ukraine), as well as the method of JSC "VNIMI" (St. Petersburg, Russia) for establishing the dimensions of chambers and pillars for chamber mining systems for non-ferrous metal ores [eleven]. The stressed state of the rock mass, which determines the stability of the excavation outcrop, is formed under the influence of mining and geological factors, of which the main ones are: rock fracturing; depth of development; the angle of inclination of the outcrop to the horizon; equivalent outcrop span; time of existence of the outcrop; the nature of support or the order of part-time work [11]. The stability of the outcrop is characterized by the size of the equivalent span. Calculations of chamber parameters were made based on the following conditions: stable ore and host rocks with medium fracturing, strength according to the prof. scale. Protodyakonov 12–18, the deposits dip angle is more than 500; When the thickness of ore bodies is 3–15 m, the system of development by sublevel drifts is used, and if the thickness of ore bodies is more than 15 m, by sublevel ores [12].

Floor height 60 and 70 m, subfloor height 15–18 m; the order of mining the sub-levels is ground-yielding, drilling with ascending fans of holes with a diameter of 57 and 65 mm, which were drilled with NT-2 "Norit" and PK-75 rigs. Parallel downward wells with a diameter of 85 mm to form a cutting slot were drilled using NKR-100M rigs. The broken ore was supplied to VG-4M cars through vibrating feeders PVG-1.2/3.1 and PVG-1.3/7.0. Self-propelled drilling equipment of domestic production is also used for tunneling and clearing operations. In particular, the BU-85S drilling rig; column for drilling holes with a hand-held hammer drill LKR-MN; mine drilling rig UBSH-201; mine drilling rig UBSH-203; small-sized drilling rig UBSH-1GL and loading and hauling equipment: loading and hauling machine MPDN-1A; electro-hydraulic loading and transport machine PT-2ESH-M, as well as foreign companies "Atlas Copco" (drilling rigs Boomer 281, Boomer S1D; loading and hauling machine Wagner ST-3.5; mine dump trucks MT 2010, SANY LC 20E), "Tamrock", etc. The voids are filled with a hardening fill with a strength of 1.5 to 6.0 MPa [13, 14].

Theory of the issue.

Graphic-analytical method for calculating the stability of outcrops of host rocks and the backfill mass. The geometric parameters of the system for developing sublevel drifts for ore deposits with a horizontal thickness of up to 15 m, when the length of the chamber along strike is 2 - 3 times or more greater than the width (thickness), are given below. For operational monitoring of the stress-strain state (SSS) of the rock massif, sound measuring instruments were used, in particular, portable ones as the simplest means and methods of observation (developed by the scientific and production complex of automation and mechanics (NPK "A and M"), manufactured jointly with the mechanical repair plant (RMZ) of the State Enterprise " Vostok-GOK ", Ukraine) and others.

Based on the results of full-scale tests of rock mass elements carried out at uranium deposits of Ukraine, the dependences of the frequency of elastic sounds of destruction on the magnitude of stresses σ were constructed, taking into account the safety factor (K_s), which is expressed as the ratio of the maximum (destructive) load $[\sigma]$ acting on the structural element σ , or as the ratio of the ultimate strength of the material to the design stress, according to the formulas:

$$\sigma = a \cdot N_u^b \quad (1)$$

$$K_s = [\sigma] / \sigma \quad (2)$$

where N_u – is the number of pulses per minute; a and b are, respectively, coefficients characterizing the structural and strength properties of the rock mass.

Based on formulas (1) and (2), with a sufficient degree of accuracy it is possible to predict the dependence of the frequency of destruction sounds on the magnitude of fracture stresses and the safety factor based on the intensity of the recorded sound pulses.

For complex-structured ore deposits in energy-disturbed massifs, the value of the stable span of a flat unsupported roof between pillars supporting rocks inside the limiting arch of natural equilibrium was calculated based on the idea of the distribution of acting forces in the arch of natural equilibrium. An analysis of the ratio between the standard and actual strength of the hardening filling mixture shows that the discrepancy between their values is 20–50%.

Based on the known values of the equivalent span, the length and width of the outcrop are determined from the expressions:

$$a = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma}{L_{\sigma K_s}}\right)^2 - 1}} \quad \sigma = \frac{a}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{a}{L_{\sigma K_s}}\right)^2 - 1}} \quad (3)$$

The lifetime of the outcrop is taken into account by the time coefficient (K_B) (Fig. 1):

$$K_B = \sqrt{\frac{t_1}{t_0}} \quad (4)$$

where t_1 – is the time during which the camera can be worked during intensive work, months; t_0 – initial estimated working time, months.

Figure 1. Nomogram for determining the coefficient of change in the length of the chamber from the time of its mining and backfilling: 1, 2 - respectively, the chamber goes under the backfill and the ore (rock) pillar; key: A–B–C–Q1; D–E–F– K_B (other designations in the text).

For cameras facing the enclosed space, the K_B value varies from 0.76 to 1.10 and is determined according to the formula:

$$t_1 = 0,5t_2 + t_3 = 6 \text{ мес} \quad (5)$$

where, t_2 – respectively, the time of breaking off the chamber reserves and t_3 – standing until it is completely filled, months.

For chambers extending under the ore massif, the value of K_B varies from 0.92 to 1.23 and is determined according to the formula:

$$t_1 = 0,5t_2 + t_3 = 12 \text{ мес} \quad (6)$$

$$t_0 = 0,5t_2 + t_3 \quad (7)$$

Based on the results of many years of research carrying out a complex of scientific research work in the underground development of complex-structured ore deposits in energy-disturbed massifs, the authors propose calculation formulas for justifying the safe and effective parameters of the chambers, taking into account the stability of their outcrops (Table 1).

Table 1.

Safe parameters of chambers for ore deposits	
Name of parameters	Calculation formulas
1. Equivalent spans at outcrops, m:	
correct shape;	$L_{\text{ЭКВ}} = \frac{a \cdot B}{\sqrt{a^2 + B^2}}$
irregular shape	$L_{\text{ЭКВ}} = \frac{2,5 \cdot S}{P_0}$
2. Outcrop stability criterion, m	$L_{\text{ЭКВ}} = L_{\text{ЭДОП}} = \frac{L_{\text{Э0}}}{1,1}$
3. Stable spans, m:	
horizontal	$L_{\text{Г.ЭКВ}} = \frac{a \cdot B}{\sqrt{a^2 + B^2}}$
vertical	$L_{\text{В.ЭКВ}} = \frac{a \cdot H}{\sqrt{a^2 + H^2}}$
4. Equivalent span ($L_{\text{Э0}}$, m) taking into account the existence time of outcrops (t , months)	$L_{\text{Э0}}^2 \cdot t = \text{const} = A$
5. Equivalent spans for laying, m	
horizontal;	$L_{\text{Г.ЭКВ}} = \sqrt{\frac{2\sigma_{\text{ИЗ}} \cdot h_{\text{СЛ}}}{\gamma_3 \cdot K_3}}$
vertical	$L_{\text{В.ЭКВ}} = \frac{2C_{\text{М}}}{\gamma_3 \cdot K_3} \text{ctg} \left(45^\circ + \frac{\rho}{2} \right)$
6. Stability of outcrops, m:	
length (a);	$a = \frac{L_{\text{Г.ЭКВ}} \cdot b}{\sqrt{b^2 + L_{\text{Г.ЭКВ}}^2}}$
width (b);	$b = \frac{L_{\text{Г.ЭКВ}}^2 \cdot a}{\sqrt{a^2 + L_{\text{Г.ЭКВ}}^2}}$
height (H)	$H = \frac{L_{\text{Г.ЭКВ}} \cdot a}{\sqrt{a^2 + L_{\text{Г.ЭКВ}}^2}}$
<p>Note. The formulas indicate: S и P_0 – area and perimeter of the outcrop, m^2 and m, respectively; A is a constant value, the value of which depends on the properties of the rock mass and is determined from experience, units (for complex-structured ore deposits of the State Enterprise " VostokGOK ", Ukraine in energy-disturbed massifs, the value A varies from 26800 (highly fractured massif) to 220000 (weakly fractured massif) with horizontal when the massif is exposed and from 75000 (highly fractured massif) to 1060000 (weakly fractured massif) – when hanging wall rocks are exposed); $\sigma_{\text{ИЗ}}$ – is the bending strength of the fill, t/m^2; $h_{\text{СЛ}}$ – thickness of the lower monolithic layer of the fill (in calculations it was assumed $h_{\text{СЛ}} = 4 \text{ m}$); γ_3 – filling density, t/m^3; K_3 – safety factor (in calculations it is assumed $K_3 = 3$); $C_{\text{М}}$ – coefficients of adhesion between the backfill and ore, t/m^2; ρ – angle of internal friction (in calculations it was assumed $\rho = 32^\circ$)</p>	

To ensure the safety of mining operations in the zone influenced by the voids of waste chambers, the following was carried out:

forecast of stress-strain state of a rock mass and assessment of the conditions for the dynamic manifestation of rock pressure;

organization of a geomechanical monitoring system for the stress-strain state of the mountain range and the stability of chamber outcrops; equipping mines with

equipment and instruments for its implementation; training mine personnel to conduct observations and control of the stress-strain state of the mountain range.

The geometric parameters of the chambers, length (a), width (b), as well as the values of the equivalent horizontal and vertical spans, ensuring the stability of the backfill mass, are found according to the dependencies (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Nomogram for determining the length of the chamber depending on the maximum permissible equivalent span of the horizontal outcrop

In the primary chambers, the permissible equivalent span of outcrops depends on the strength of the host rocks of the ore and the depth of development (Fig. 3).

The equivalent span of a horizontal outcrop with a thickness of ore bodies up to 3 m and a compressive strength of the backfill of more than 3.0 MPa can be of unlimited length [15].

Figure 3. Nomogram for determining the length of the chamber (a) depending on the maximum equivalent span of the hanging wall rock outcrop ($L^{6.б.}_{экв}$) and the development depth (H): 1, 2 – respectively, chamber height 60m and 70m

Initial data on the hardening fill. In recent years, there has been a significant change in the assessment of the impact of underground work on the environment. The development of environmental trends prioritizes the conservation of the earth's surface and human health over economic considerations. This is achieved mainly through the use of ore extraction technology with backfilling of mined-out space, the share of which in the total volume of mineral extraction exceeds 60% and this figure is limited by the high cost and scarcity of backfill components [16].

Therefore, one of the directions for solving this problem is to optimize the main parameter - the standard strength of artificial massifs, taking into account the relationship between the geomechanical characteristics of rock massifs and the effectiveness of their management from the standpoint of preserving the earth's surface.

The stability of horizontal and vertical backfill outcrops is directly dependent on the quality of the backfill mixture, hardening time and solidity (Fig.4).

Figure 4. Strength characteristics of the backfill depending on the hardening period (t): 1,2, 3 – respectively, adhesion coefficient (C), bending strength (σ_{iz}) and tensile strength (σ_p), MPa; key: A–B–C; A–D–E; A–K–F.

The strength of the rock-backfill contact in bending and tension is equal to the strength of the backfill according to these indicators. The angle of internal friction (ρ) is assumed to be 32° .

The solidity of the filling depends on the degree of stratification of the mixture during breaks when laying the chambers. A change in the ratio of the constituent components in the exfoliated part of the fill reduces the calculated strength properties by more than 1/3 [17].

The graphic-analytical method for determining the safe parameters of chambers when developing ore deposits of complex structure allows solving a number of problems:

- selection of development systems with backfilling for individual deposits, taking into account their geomorphological and geomechanical features;

- determination of safe geometric parameters of production blocks depending on the time of its development and spatial position in the host rock mass, as well as on the structural state of the ore and host massifs;

- establishment of safe technological parameters of the hardening mixture for backfilling the mined-out space;

- calculation of seismic safety parameters for internal mine structures and communications, as well as for surface industrial buildings and mining complexes.

The intensity of mining and filling of chambers is of great importance for the stability of the massif outcrops (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Nomogram for determining the period of exposure of a hardening backfill based on its strength

Example of calculating camera parameters. *Initial data.* The thickness of the ore body is 14 m, the inclined height of the floor is 75 m, the

mining depth is 450 m, the strength of the host rocks is according to the prof. scale. M.M. Protodyakonov -14, the hardening backfill of the overlying chamber has a six-month hardening age, the operating time of the operational block is 8, and its repayment

with the hardening backfill mixture is 2 months [18, 19].

The period of exposure of the hardening backfill, its compressive strength, depending on the maximum permissible equivalent spans of horizontal and vertical exposures of the first-stage chambers, is determined by a nomogram (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Nomogram for determining the maximum equivalent span of an outcrop ceilings for the mountain range: 1, 2, 3 – respectively, strongly, moderately and weakly fractured mountain range

Solution. According to the nomogram (see Fig. 1), the permissible spans of horizontal and vertical outcrops are found, which are, respectively, 13.4 and 30 m. The intersection of the line corresponding to these values on the nomogram (see Fig. 2) with a thickness of 14 m is determined at on the vertical axis, the length of the chamber is –45 m. According to the nomogram (see Fig. 3), based on the initial data, we find that, under the conditions of an inclined outcrop of 75 m, the length of the chamber can be –51 m. The value of K_B is found according to formula (6): $t_1 = 0,5 \cdot 8 + 2 = 6$ months. In this case $K_B = 1$. Using the nomogram (see Fig. 4), you can reversely determine the required hardening time of the backfill or the working and backfilling time required to increase the length of the block, for example, up to 50 m.

By lowering the intersection point of the power curve of 14 m with the chamber length of 50 m on the horizontal axis, we obtain stable equivalent spans of outcrops $L_{Г.ЭКВ} = 13,5\text{m}$ and $L_{В.ЭКВ} = 30,5\text{m}$, (see Fig.5), $K_B = 13,5: 13,4 = 1,01$.

Thus, to increase the length of the production block, for example to 50 m, you should either start working on it for 0.5 months. later, or speed up the demolition and repayment with a hardening backfill mixture by 5 days relative to the scheduled date [20, 21].

The effectiveness of the research results obtained.

For the safe conduct of mining operations when mining ore deposits in the mines of the State Enterprise “VostokGOK, Ukraine”, “Instructions on the justification of the safe conduct of mining operations and the procedure for mining ore deposits in the mines of the State Enterprise “VostokGOK” have been compiled. It

presents the main provisions, geomechanical characteristics of uranium deposits and defines criteria for assessing the stress-strain state of the rock mass. The conditions for safe mining operations, the procedure for determining the size of dangerous zones and brittle fracture of rocks prone to the dynamic manifestation of rock pressure of various forms are described. A justification for the safe procedure for mining ore deposits within the mine field is given. Measures are given for the safe conduct of mining operations and the reduction of the dynamic manifestation of rock pressure of various forms, including seismically safe masses of charges and their influence on the safe conduct of mining operations in the depth range of 300–1000 m when mining ore deposits with chamber mining systems with backfilling of the goaf [22, 23]. As a result of a complex of research work, the modern technical level of the system used was established, taking into account the geomechanical safety of the development, its elements, parameters and dimensions of the chambers, as well as technological processes were standardized (Table 2).

To develop reserves above the mountains. -300 of the Novokonstantinovskoye ore deposit (SE “VostokGOK”, Ukraine) using chamber and layer mining systems with backfilling of the goaf, the “Instructions for the geomechanical justification for the safe development of reserves above the mountains” have been developed. -300m at the State Enterprise Directorate mine. It outlines calculation methods and presents nomograms for determining safe and stable outcrops of mining and artificial mining blocks, permissible volumes of voids in mined out, partially extinguished and isolated mined-out spaces, seismically safe masses of charges and their influence on the safe conduct of mining operations in the depth range of 300–1000 m when mining ore deposits using chamber mining systems with backfilling of mined-out space.

Table 2.

Technological parameters of the development system

Options	Value of indicators for the thickness of ore bodies, m		
	от 3 до 6	от 6 до 15	от 15 до 90
Chamber dimensions, m:			
height	60-70	60-70	60-70
length	40-70	30-60	15-90
width	3-6	6-15	12-15
Height, m:			
Subfloor;	10-13	16-20	16-20
bottoms	8-13	11	11
Distance between outlets, m	8	8-10	8-10
Volume of mining operations per 1000 tons of balance reserves of the block, m ³ ;	140-70 23,0	70-28 4,7	80-42 4,8
The procedure for processing block reserves	Through the camera		Through two chambers - reserves of the first stages of excavation, the second - through three
Direction of chamber stock removal	From center to flank or from flank to flank		From hanging side to lying side or vice versa
Procedure for clearing sub-level reserves	Soil concession		Soil concession
Formation of a cutting gap	Down up		Down up
Location of boreholes	Fan		Fan
Well diameter, mm	65 85	65 85	65 85
Ore release method	With delivery horizon	Gravity	
Output of oversized items, %	4-5	5-7	
Strength of hardening mixtures, MPa:			
for bottoms (ceilings) and chambers of the first stage of mining;	2,5	3,0	6,0
for cameras of other processing queues	1,2	1,5	2,0

The dependences of safe and stable parameters of treatment blocks on mining-geological and mining-technical conditions, physical-mechanical properties of rocks and artificial massifs and the time of exposure of mined-out spaces are given [24, 25].

A set of enterprise standards has been compiled "System of development by sublevel drifts (orths) with backfilling of mined-out space with a hardening mixture. Parameters and Dimensions", which regulates (depending on mining and geological conditions) the length, width and height of the chambers of the first, second and third stages of excavation, their maximum permissible values, taking into account changes in the strength properties of the backfill during its hardening and the depth of development, the height of the subfloor and the bottom of the block, the distance between the outlet loading and delivery workings (decks) depending on the thickness of the ore body and the height of the floor, the shape and dimensions of the cross sections of the main side workings.

Technological parameters of the development system: the equipment used, the method and mechanization of ore release, the procedure for mining and blasting chamber reserves, the location and diameter of drill holes - are also determined depending on the previously

standardized parameters and dimensions of the chambers.

To strictly regulate the requirements for the main parameters (taking into account the design features of the system used) and to extinguish the mined-out space with a hardening mixture, other technological processes and elements of underground mining technology have been standardized in specific mining and geological conditions of complex-structured ore deposits in energy-damaged massifs of the State Enterprise "VostokGOK", Ukraine (STP – "Deposit preparation schemes", "Parameters and design of block bottoms", "Drilling and blasting operations. Parameters and dimensions", "Filling of mined-out space with a hardening mixture", etc.).

This set of standards has been implemented at mining enterprises in Ukraine and is successfully used by specialists of technological and geological surveying services [26, 27]. Based on the results of assessing the level of stress state of the rock mass and the mechanism of manifestation of rock pressure based on visual signs, the authors developed a classification of the stress state of the rock mass depending on the orientation of the maximum stresses relative to the workings (Table 3) [28, 29].

Geomechanical monitoring of rock masses and pillars for various purposes. It is carried out through complex methods and various surveying tools and systems. In particular, sound measuring and surveying instruments, string strain gauges, depth and soil benchmarks, optical instruments, electrical circuits, visual and indirect methods for changing the mineralization of mine waters. For operational monitoring and forecasting of VAT and pillars for various purposes, sound measuring instruments are used. To study the process of deformation and destruction of rock masses, ores and backfill masses, to determine the magnitude of deformations and the boundaries of the zone of influence of the clearing space, string strain gauges, depth and soil benchmarks are used [30, 31].

Promising areas of research.

The authors of the article consider promising the research and implementation of combined technologies and means, when rich ores are brought to the surface and processed at the GMZ, and poor and substandard ores are leached in underground blocks (UB) and stacks on the earth's surface (bunch leaching) to produce metals, construction raw materials, demineralized water, gases, acids and lowgrade alkalis.

Such technologies are effective when 40% of high-grade ore is exposed to the surface, and 60% of low-grade, substandard and off-balance ore is leached underground. Substandard materials will be used to extinguish man-made cavities and subsequent extraction of metals or use them to backfill underground roads and rail tracks.

Table 3.

Classification of the stress state of the rock massif

Place of manifestation of disturbance in production	Form and intensity of the violation	Orientation σ_{max}	Array stress level	Impact category	
There are no violations along the entire perimeter	Contouring of excavations along natural weakening surfaces	Vertical	$\eta \leq 0,12$	Nonshock hazardous	
In the heels of the arch and walls on both sides	Peeling in the depressions at the tips of joints of cracks of natural separation	Vertical	$0,12 < \eta \leq 0,2$		
	Local stratification of structural blocks along the "live"		$0,2 < \eta \leq 0,3$		III
	Exfoliation along the "live" side, "barreling" of workings.		$0,3 < \eta \leq 0,5$		II
	Dynamic spalling, buckling of non-impact rocks		$\eta > 0,5$	I	
In the middle of the arch	Peeling in the depressions at the tips of joints of cracks of natural separation	Horizontally	$0,12 < \eta \leq 0,2$	Nonshock hazardous	
	Local stratification of structural blocks along the "live"		$0,2 < \eta \leq 0,3$	III	
	Exfoliation along the "live" side, "barreling" of workings.		$0,3 < \eta \leq 0,5$	II	
	Dynamic spalling, buckling of non-impact rocks		$\eta > 0,5$	I	
Displacement of the source of disturbance from the arch lock	Peeling in the depressions at the tips of joints of cracks of natural separation	Tangent to the surface of the violation	$0,12 < \eta \leq 0,2$	Nonshock hazardous	
	Local stratification of structural blocks along the "live"		$0,2 < \eta \leq 0,3$	III	
	Exfoliation along the "live" side, "barreling" of workings.		$0,3 < \eta \leq 0,5$	II	
	Dynamic spalling, buckling of non-impact rocks		$\eta > 0,5$	I	

Creation and implementation of radiometric technologies and technical means for the enrichment of uranium ores based on their sorting in underground conditions and processing of uranium industry dumps using modular separator installations such "Alunit", "Laurit R 40", "Albit R 90" and "Altait" (developer – scientific and production complex of automation and mechanics

NPK "A and M", Ukraine), and showed positive practical results [1].

Separation of laying materials

At mining enterprises, vibration, mechanical and electrochemical activation devices are used to obtain a hardening backfill mixture with a strength of 0.2–1.2 MPa using local materials. When producing a low-strength filler, it is necessary to ensure fine grinding,

destruction of loosely bound pieces of filler and a stable transportation mode. This is carried out by vibration activation of inert materials, mechanical activation of binders before mixing, vibration activation of the hardening filling mixture during its transportation and electrochemical activation of water. Vibration activation of inert fillers during screening is possible in the case when stress concentrations are created in a piece of material sufficient for its destruction.

Mechanical activation of binding materials is carried out in grinders, for example, a ball mill with central unloading MShTs 3200x4500 (Ukraine). However, the most effective are high-speed devices, for example, disintegrator-activators type DU-65 (Disintegrator company, Tallinn, Estonia) and a vertical vibration mill type MVV-0.7 (Ukraine). It is advisable to carry out vibration activation of the hardening filling mixture during its transportation through pipelines to the place of installation. The vertical vibratory mill MVV-0.7 for grinding granulated slag is installed in the technological chain after the disintegrator. Due to the high vibration frequency, the crushed material experiences one to two orders of magnitude more impacts per unit time than in ball mills. The mill is disconnected from the circuit and the material is loaded directly into it. The vibration amplitude of the mill is 6.5 mm, and the magnitude of the driving force is 190.0 kN [32, 33].

Thus, the development of preventive measures to minimize the negative consequences on the health of workers in the mining and metallurgical industries is a priority scientific, practical and social task that requires urgent solutions. It is proposed to continue research and provide appropriate funds (at the expense of enterprises, local and central government bodies) for carrying out urgent environmental and social measures when mining of ferrous, non-ferrous and radioactive metals.

For example, according to the "State program of measures for radiation and social protection of the population of the city of Zhovti Vody, Dnepropetrovsk region" (Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers dated June 8, 1995 No. 400; dated May 5, 2003 No. 656 and dated June 25, 2012 No. 579) [19].

Based on the results of many years of research on the implementation of a complex of scientific research work in the underground development of deposits of complex structure in energy-damaged massifs of the State Enterprise "VostokGOK", the following conclusions were made.

Conclusions.

A functional relationship is shown between the magnitude of the stresses of the rock mass and the number of pulses (sounds of destruction) per minute, which characterize its structural (**a**) and strength (**b**) properties, described by a curvilinear dependence of the form $y = ax^b$. This allows you to quickly establish stable parameters and dimensions of the cameras with a probability of 0.8.

It has been established that the permissible equivalent span of a horizontal outcrop with a uniaxial compressive strength of the hardening fill of more than 3.0 MPa is always less than the vertical one. If the width of the chamber is less than the equivalent span of the horizontal outcrop, its length is limited by the stability of

the vertical outcrop, and for chambers located along the strike of the ore deposits - by the stability of the hanging wall host rocks.

The geometric parameters of the chambers and the stability of vertical and horizontal outcrops depend on the intensity of mining and backfilling of the chambers. The faster the camera is worked out and laid, the more exposure is allowed.

For the efficient operation of mining enterprises, including ferrous metallurgy mines, it is necessary to provide high-quality binding components for the preparation of hardening mixtures for filling technogenic voids formed during the underground development of solid mineral deposits. It has been established that the use of vibration, mechanical and electrical activation of the components of the hardening filling mixture at mining enterprises leads to an increase in the activity of substandard materials by up to 10–40% for each apparatus. In particular, enrichment of inert materials on a vibrating screen GV-1.2/3.2, Ukraine.

Increases activity by 15–20%. It has been substantiated that the activation of binder materials (blast furnace granulated slag) in a vertical vibratory mill MVV-0.7 and a disintegrator DU-65 from the Disintegrator company increases the activity of the binder by 20 – 25%, and with the output of the active class of fractions with a particle size of 0.074 mm – by 55% versus 40% in ball mills. Recommended vibrotransport installations increase the activity of the components of the hardening backfill mixture by 10–15% [34, 35].

A graphic-analytical method (nomograms and calculation formulas) is recommended for justifying the safe parameters of the chambers based on the results of many years of research in the underground development of deposits of complex structure, depending on the properties of the rock mass and is determined from experience for a strongly, moderately and weakly fractured rock mass with its horizontal exposure. The "Instructions for the geomechanical justification of safe mining of reserves at the mines of the State Enterprise "VostokGOK", Ukraine" have also been compiled [36].

Prospective studies. It is proposed to continue research and provide appropriate funds (at the expense of enterprises, local and central government bodies) to carry out urgent environmental and social measures [19]:

- widespread involvement in the production of technogenic reserves of ore enrichment tailings, as well as the processing of off-balance ore dumps in terms of the content of useful components in modular plants;
- deep processing of technogenic waste (concentration tailings), which has a wide variety of mineral forms compared to conventional ores;
- scientific substantiation and development of preventive measures to minimize the negative consequences on human health from the effects of heavy metals and radiation factors, taking into account the characteristics of their combined influence on the population and workers of the uranium mining and metallurgical industries;
- reclamation of the territory of industrial sites and the adjacent territory after the end of operation.

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